

IDEA: Incorporating Diversity into the Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers

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FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON

	Factors	Suggestion solutions
1	Lack of clear and transparent promotion criteria	Transparent, unambiguous and well-communicated promotion criteria
2	Disproportionally high workloads of invisible service work	Equal distribution of labor
3	Sexism and racial discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Acknowledge identity in knowledge production over 'objectivity'• Promote inclusivity, diversity, and equity through policies and trainings, and monitor• Role models
4	Exclusion from professional and support networks	Culturally competent mentorship
5	Precarious working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Support for parents and caretakers• Do not expect uniform productivity
6	Lack of (financial) support for engaging in true research interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Provide growth possibilities• Reward and value research on diversity, equity and inclusion

*Findings from literature review

QUESTIONS TO EXPLORE

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- How attractive is VU as an employer for different demographic and professional groups?
- Will the proposed changes meaningfully impact the balance between valuing teaching and research?
- To what extent do ambiguous promotion criteria pose a barrier to achieving diversity?
- How do current criteria limit mobility and interdisciplinarity within VU?
- Why is there no specific targeting of PhD candidates or Team Science initiatives, and what are the implications?

*Findings from workshop #1 IDEA

MAPPING DIVERSITY WITHIN FACULTY POLICIES

BETA: Diversity is explicitly stated as a goal, but no explanation of what it entails. The policy mentions actions like bias training, diverse committees, and inclusive recruitment practices.

Diversity addressed in policies?

BETA ACTA SOC HUM

BETA: There are many criteria, but it's not always clear how they're balanced. Mention of clear red flags.
ACTA: Includes examples for five categories, with checkboxes showing what's expected at each level — Junior, Medior, Senior, and Expert.
SOC: Mention of service work for all profiles and positions.
HUM: Procedure to become a full professor is missing, as it's covered elsewhere. Salary scales are included.

Policy developers known?

BETA ACTA SOC HUM

Clear and transparent criteria?

Research
Teaching
Impact
Leadership
Care

BETA ACTA SOC HUM

ACTA: Rubrics should be developed with narratives where staff explain any leave taken (parental, illness, care). It's not clear whether this affects the evaluation process.

Consideration of care-taking roles

BETA
ACTA
SOC
HUM

Committee diversity addressed?

BETA ACTA SOC HUM

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OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

- Most policies mention a mix of qualitative and quantitative indicators.
- There is an underlying assumption that everyone should aim for vertical growth from UD2-UD1-UHD2-UHD2-HL
- BETA policy mentions equal division of tasks among staff with concrete suggestions.
- SOC policy explicitly mentions and rewards service work for all profiles and positions.

Note: Implementation policies from the other faculties were not available at the time this infographic was created.

● Addressed
● Ambiguous
● Not addressed